

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 4.2

Demo 2: Monitoring agricultural land use and provision of value-added agricultural services I

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List of Acronyms

CDS	Change Detector Service
DC	Demonstration Case
EO	Earth Observation
JRC	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the implementation of pilot activities of the LandSense Agricultural Land Use theme (i.e. Demonstration Case 2, Phase I). The activities were implemented between November 2017 and September 2018 in Serbia, involving students from two agricultural high schools and a group of master students from the University of Novi Sad. The data were collected via the CropSupport application, which was also tested and evaluated by the participants. The user feedbacks from Phase I will be synthesized and analysed to guide iterative improvement of the CropSupport app and the crowdsourcing campaign for Phase II. This deliverable will also serve to feed into D4.4: Feedback and Evaluation of LandSense Demonstration Cases I.

1 Introduction

This deliverable focuses on the LandSense theme “Agricultural Land Use” and reports on the implementation of the action plan as outlined in D2.2. The pilot activities, within this theme, aim to show how citizens can be involved in monitoring agricultural land use by using the CropSupport mobile and web application for collecting data related to crop type and farm management activities. Additionally, the “Agricultural Land Use” pilot puts an emphasis on the provision of value-added agricultural services for farmers by conflating crowdsourced inputs with Earth Observation (EO) data. The CropSupport platform allows its users to access valuable information about their land – namely, weather forecast for the micro locations of their parcels as well as NDVI, vegetation and moisture indexes.

Also, iterative testing of the CropSupport application within Phase I provided useful insights and inputs for development of other LandSense services for Agricultural Land Use theme – in particular the Change Detection Service (CDS) and Data Quality Assurance Service.

In the following sections, this report will provide a detailed overview on the all activities and achievements accomplished within Phase I.

2 Agricultural Land Use theme at a glance - Demonstration Pilot (Serbia)

Monitoring Agricultural Land Use and Provision of Value-added Agricultural

The Agricultural Land Use theme focuses on leveraging the power of EO systems and advanced crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value added services to European farmers and public authorities in the agricultural sector.

OVERALL GOALS

- ✓ to demonstrate the functionalities and usefulness of the CropSupport service and to provide a far-reaching, comprehensive monitoring and decision support tool for operational farm management
- ✓ to effectively evaluate and highlight the capacities of the LandSense Citizen Observatory

SPECIFIC GOALS

- ✓ to test and validate the CropSupport application in an operational setting and to improve it for wider and sustainable use based on the experience of targeted end-users
- ✓ to empower citizen-driven observations and engagement, and obtain high-quality data within the pilot

THE MAIN BENEFITS

- ✓ Through cutting edge IT technology, INOSENS aims to help targeted individuals to acquire a better understanding of the relationship between agricultural land use change and production. Via the CropSupport application, farmers access the relevant information related to the management of daily farm activities, such as NDVI maps and weather forecast for the micro locations of their parcels.

THE MAIN UPSCALING QUALITY

- ✓ During Phase I, the CropSupport application shows immense potential for scalability in terms of stakeholders, and replicability to other geographical areas – since the application is flexible and operates in English.

FUN FACT

Our approach establishes a sound “build, measure, learn” framework for conducting pilot activities to blend citizen science with **gamification**. Within Phase I, the pilot engaged student teams and teachers from two agriculture high schools. The teams competed with each other to provide as much crowdsourced Land Use & Land Cover (LULC) data about agricultural land through the CropSupport application. Being digital natives, students crave interactivity, and through our pilot activities, they were able to use CropSupport to immerse themselves in authentic field settings and receive first-hand experience collecting in-situ data.

3 Achievements

3.1 Development and testing of CropSupport application

The pilot activities were implemented between November 2017 and September 2018 in accordance with the action plan (D2.2). By November 2017, the prototype of the CropSupport mobile and web application was already developed and ready to be tested. Also, as an extension of the CropSupport web application, the Administrator Panel was developed to support monitoring of the crowdsourcing campaign (i.e. a user commitment and quality of collected data).

3.2 Demonstration of citizen science approach

The citizen science approach was demonstrated by engaging over **60 students** from two agricultural high-schools and the University of Novi Sad. Prior to the student engagement, a detailed timeline of the pilot activities was prepared along with the supporting material (e.g. invitation letters, explanatory text & video, LandSense leaflet, Facebook profile). Also, particular attention had been given to informing local and regional media about the LandSense project and the pilot activities in Serbia, where the concept of citizen science was introduced to wider community.

3.3 Obtaining agricultural in-situ data

Through empowering citizen-driven observations of agricultural LULC, a significant amount of in-situ data was acquired. Namely, the planned Phase I's KPIs were achieved, and the following data was collected: geotagged photographs of crops, delineated crop parcels, farm management activities (e.g. crop type, seeding, tillage & harvesting date). However – the quality of collected data has to be carefully assessed, as the participants were involved for the first time in crowdsourcing activities using mobile devices and PCs.

3.4 Added value service for farmers

Besides being a tool for in-situ data collection and sharing, the CropSupport application offers to its users several added value services – such as NDVI maps, parcel-based weather forecast, and a farm activity diary. The majority of the Phase I's participants used EO related products for the first time, which helped them acquire new and relevant knowledge. This was especially beneficial for those participants that are members of farm households, as they shared newly acquired knowledge and information to other members of their family and their farming community.

4 Target Groups

The Agricultural Land Use pilot (Phase I) targeted high school and university students as key groups for testing and validation of the CropSupport application in an operational environment (Table 2). The group of agricultural high-school students were seen as an entry point for promoting citizens science within the farming community because majority of the students come from families involved in agri-food business. On the other hand, the Masters students from the University of Novi Sad were identified as active stakeholders in the EO ecosystem and possible users of the LandSense services in future.

The general motivation used to attract students to participate in the pilot activities – acquisition of new, relevant and practical knowledge related to the use of the modern technology in agricultural sector were offered. Additionally, as a reward for participation in pilot activities, the high-school students received t-shirts with the LandSense project and CropSupport app logos, USB memory stick and participation certificates. Also, the two high-schools received a laptop, as a gift to be used for promotion and demonstration of agri-tech solutions during the classes (such as CropSupport application). On the other hand, the University students were offered the certificates of participation, which they could utilize as a proof of doing a practical training within the Geo-informatic course – a task obligatory within their curriculum (Annex 1).

Table 2. Target groups

Target groups (from D2.2)	Experiences, barriers, helping factors
<p>High-school students</p>	<p>Students were involved to stimulate interest in the use of CropSupport and the subsequent crowdsourcing campaigns. The pilot activities generated interest in applying EO based technology within the agricultural sector, while the campaign was reported to be a fun activity which encouraged the students to work in groups and to utilise their smartphones for farming related activities.</p> <p>The most common barriers encountered during the campaign was related to poor performance of some of the students’ smartphones (e.g. GPS device out of function, lack of memory space, etc.). However, group work proved to be a helping factor, as those students having problems with their smartphones, were able to borrow a mobile device from their companions. Finally, consistent engagement of the students to collect data through the entirety of the campaign was necessary as the students were not used to participate in similar activities before.</p>

<p>University students (Geoinformatics discipline)</p>	<p>As potential end-users of the application in the future, the Masters students were perceived as a very important group that can provide valuable feedback related to the CropSupport application. For the students, the engagement in the campaign represented a good opportunity to acquire practical knowledge and to become familiar with a new technology.</p> <p>The most common barrier faced by this group was related to lack of agricultural knowledge. Namely, in contrast to the agricultural high-school students that were able to easily differentiate crops, the master students had difficulties to do the same. In order to overcome this barrier, a detailed presentation about the most common crop types in the region along with printed manual were prepared and disseminated to students.</p>
<p>Farmers and other users</p>	<p>Although the farmers were not the focus of the Phase I campaign activities, some of them voluntarily joined the campaign, because they learned about CropSupport application and its usefulness from the students and/or from local media.</p>

5 Engagement strategies

5.1 High-school students

By early June 2017, the INOSENS pilot team connected with the two agricultural high-schools’ administrations in order to introduce the program and to receive support in this endeavour¹. The initial contact was made by a phone call, followed by official invitation for participation in LandSense demonstration activities sent by email. Upon receiving the positive answers, separate face-to-face meetings with the two school principals were organised. Each principal specified teachers responsible for communication with INOSENS team and for facilitating active engagement of the students.

The teachers helped us to reach out to the motivated students willing to participate in the pilot activities by promoting the campaign during their lectures. To ensure active student engagement, the promotion of the pilot activities was combined with a gaming approach in the form of a competition. As a result, a list of teams was established – 5 teams of the 5-6 students per school.

During the November 2017, the workshop “The Start line” was organised at each school, where promotion of the pilot activities was packaged in a lecture about remote sensing and sustainable agriculture. The students received training and tutorials on how to use CropSupport² along with written guidance (Annex 1). In addition, the rules of the competition and scoring system were clearly explained. For example: Creating an activity - 0.5 pts, invitation to register - 1pt, creating a parcel - 2pt, and taking a photo of a parcel - 1pt.

¹ The two schools contacted and involved into the pilot activities are: (i) Srednja poljoprivredno-prehrambena škola “Stevan Petrović Brile”, Ruma; (ii) Poljoprivredna škola Bač, Bač.

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wZENne1-QJ8>

After the initial workshops, the students were encouraged to use the CropSupport application for data collection. The INOSENS team maintained regular contact with the teachers in order to monitor the progress and eventual challenges faced by the teams. Also, the students had the possibility to contact INOSENS team via CropSupport web's messenger and with FaceBook page³ with specific questions.

During April 2018, another two workshops, named "The halfway point" were held. The purpose of these workshops was to sustain engagement of the students in pilot activities, to accelerate the competition during the spring period and to get the students' feedback on the use of the CropSupport app.

The last workshop, named "The finish line" were held at the end of June (before the summer holiday), when the results of the campaign was presented to the participants. All students received participation certificates, while the members of the most active team won a prize (working uniforms and T-shirts) (Annex 1). This event was utilized for acquiring detailed feedback from the participants on their experienced and use of the CropSupport application. Finally, the students were encouraged to continue to use CropSupport application, while those coming from farm families were informed about possibility to be involved in Phase II pilot activities as a farm household.

5.2 University students

Masters students from the University of Novi Sad were involved in pilot activities from March until September 2018. A similar engagement strategy to one that was used for involvement of the high-school students was employed. Namely, three workshops were held:

- (i) **INTRODUCTION** (1st workshop) – the students were informed about LandSense, citizen science concepts, remote sensing/EO in agricultural sector, and the LandSense agricultural pilots. Also, the main channel for communication, in the form of an e-mail group, was set-up in order to enable the students to reach out to the campaign leader (i.e. INOSENS team) in case they face difficulties while collecting in-situ data.
- (ii) **SUSTAIN** (2nd workshop) – this event was organized in June 2018 in order to sustain engagement of the users and to collect their first round of feedback.
- (iii) **FEEDBACK** (3rd workshop) – this event was organised in September 2018 in cooperation with project partner Joint European Centre (JRC). The purpose of this workshop was to officially close the Phase I pilot activities and to provide the feedback to the campaign participants on their activities and achievements. Hence, the results of the campaign were presented to the users (e.g. amount of the data collected, number of the participants, geographical distribution of data, etc.). Also, the JRC representative illustrated possibility for scientific exploitation of collected in-situ data and its conflation with EO technologies. Also, as a part of "Feedback" activities, a field trip with the JRC was organised. Namely, we used high definition cameras mounted on the roof of a car to test possibilities for improvements of agricultural in-situ data collection and validation (Annex 3).

³ <https://www.facebook.com/CropSupport/>

6 Overview of app/prototype

Within Phase I the prototype of the CropSupport website and mobile application was developed and tested. Currently, the mob application is available only for “Android” devices⁴. This section describes the workflow of the application.

6.1 Web application

The CropSupport web-based application⁵ is a interactive platform that can be accessed once users register for an account. Once the application is opened, the main user interface appears.

CROPSUPPORT USER INTERFACE

The main user interface provides access to several functions:

- (i) Base layer imagery from Google over which user draws field parcels. The map can be zoomed in/out.
- (ii) Indication and location of photos taken via mobile app (which appear on the user board).
- (iii) Possibility to outline the contours of the parcel via ‘Draw Polygon’ button (on the top left-hand side of the screen, beneath the ‘Zoom Out’ button).

⁴ <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=rs.inosense.landense>

⁵ <https://landense.inosens.rs>

PARCELS

My parcels

Parcel filter

Parcel name

Crop type

Corn (parcel 1)

Created date: 11.06.2018
 Taken pictures: 1
 Crop type: /
 Number of activities: 0

Corn (parcel 2)

Created date: 11.06.2018
 Taken pictures: 1
 Crop type: /
 Number of activities: 0

Wheat (parcel 3)

Created date: 11.06.2018
 Taken pictures: 1
 Crop type: /
 Number of activities: 0

Big one, KC55-5-5

Weather for date: 20.10.2017, 21.10.2017, 22.10.2017, 23.10.2017, 24.10.2017

Temperature

Pressure

Precipitation

Humidity Wind speed and direction Clouds

Map index

11.09.2017

- Google
- Agriculture
- Moisture Index
- Natural colors
- Vegetation Index

By selecting this function, the user is opening a new screen, where a list of created parcels can be seen. Each created parcel can be edited, deleted or selected. If a certain parcel is selected, a new window allows the user to acquire different information related to the parcel - weather forecast and NDVI maps. Also, this section allows user to access to “Activity timeline”, where s/he can take notes and keep records of variety of agricultural activities such as: tillage, planting, fertigation, plant protection and harvesting.

IMAGES

This functionality allows the user to gain an overview of all the photos s/he has taken. Each of the images could be deleted. On the other hand, if user clicks on a photo, s/he will obtain more specific information of the photo – it’s location and crop type).

MESSAGES

This section allows user to communicate with a CropSupport administrator in a case the user encountered some technical problems. Also, this communication channel could be used for communication between campaign leader and data collectors.

ABOUT, FAQ

“About” section allows user to obtain more information about the CropSupport application and the LandSense project. The “FAQ” section allows user to obtain information on how to use the application and all other relevant information related to the LandSense project.

6.2 Mobile application

The CropSupport mobile application can be downloaded at the Google Play Store. After installing the application, the user needs to sign-in by entering his/her email address and password.

DATA COLLECTION

The CropSupport mobile application is used for taking photos and entering basic information about agricultural land use (crop name; crop type). While, taking a photo of a parcel, a user must consider “accuracy” parameter which has to be below 20m. User does not need access to the internet in order to take a photo. Once the mobile device is connected to Internet, taken images will be automatically synchronized with the user web application.

7 Uptake & Performance Measures

Measuring and monitoring of the users’ contributions was done by the CropSupport web-based Administrator Panel. Besides monitoring of the user performance, the administrator panel can be used for checking validity and reliability of collected data.

USERS

Via the main dashboard of the administration panel, a particular user contribution/activity can be monitored, such as number of: parcels, images, and activities (data related to farm activities such as seeding, fertilization, irrigation, etc.). Also, the user statistic provides specific information which help assess the quality of the user data sets - number of images connected with the parcels, number of images without parcels and parcels without activities.

IMAGE VALIDITY CONTROL

The Image validity control helps for monitoring and checking the collected data. In particular, this service enables the administrator to compare the content of image with the user's claim. In this way, misinterpretation of certain land use can be minimized, as inappropriate images will be deleted and a generic message will be sent to the user informing and explaining to him/her why the image was deleted. Also, low-quality images, where there is no possibility to recognised crop type (e.g. to dark or blurry images), will be deleted. This service is quite important for the campaign where participants are not experts and could not easily differentiate types of crops.

STATISTICS – AGREGATED DATA

Group	Statistic	Value
Ruma school	Sum of parcels	185
	Sum of pictures	147
	Sum of activities	98
	Sum of pictures with parcels	118
	Sum of pictures without parcels	0
Sum of parcels without activities	104	
Bač school	Sum of parcels	221
	Sum of pictures	132
	Sum of activities	110
	Sum of pictures with parcels	101
	Sum of pictures without parcels	0
Sum of parcels without activities	166	
CropSupport users	Sum of parcels	1275
	Sum of pictures	1521
	Sum of activities	131
	Sum of pictures with parcels	1108
	Sum of pictures without parcels	0
Sum of parcels without activities	1171	
Sum of sums	Sum of parcels	1681
	Sum of pictures	1820
	Sum of activities	339
	Sum of pictures with parcels	1327
	Sum of pictures without parcels	0
Sum of parcels without activities	1441	

The main tool for monitoring the collected data is the “Statistics” panel which provides insights of overall performance for defined group of users and/or for whole campaign (different schools, group of students, etc.). Same as for individual users, aggregated data on total number of parcels, images and activities is available. Also, specific information related to quality of the group data sets are shown (number of images connected with the parcels, number of images without parcels and parcels without activities).

Phase I of the pilot is considered to be very successful and in line with the action plan (D2.2) (Table 2).

Table 2. Overview of the Phase I metrics

Metrics	Targets	Achieved
Number of mobile app installs:	Not specified	70 (50+ at Google play)
Number of registered users (web application)	Not specified	181
Number of engaged and active users	35 +	54 high school students 10 university master students 10 other users (voluntarily joined campaign)
Number of delineated parcels:	Not specified	1688
Number of images:	1750 +	1822
Number of activities ⁶	175 +	344

8 Communication outreach, media mentions

Throughout the whole implementation period of the Phase I, special attention was dedicated to communication of the pilot activities to the key target groups and to the local and regional media (Figure 1 and Table 3). The engaging information package was created, where the values of the pilot activities were clearly identified and communicated. Besides the local and regional media, the social media were used as the communication channels – such as LandSense, CropSupport and INOSENS Twitter and Facebook accounts (see Annex 2).

Figure 1. Coverage of the LandSense project in printed magazine EkoList

⁶ This metric is referring to data related to the farm related activities such as date of seeding, plowing, harvesting, etc.

Table 3. Overview of the local and regional media coverage of the pilot activities

Specialised (agricultural, environmental) online media	
	http://www.agrodan.rs/vesti/zastita-zivotne-sredine/medunarodni-projekat-landsense.html
	http://www.agrosmart.net/inovacije/projekat-landsense-dovodi-nove-tehnologije.html
	http://ekolist.org/radionica-u-rumi-ucenicima-predstav%E2%80%8Bljen%E2%80%8B-projekat-landsense-koncept-gradjanskih-opervatorija/
	https://www.energetskiportal.rs/radionica-o-znacaju-primene-informacionih-i-komunikacionih-tehnologija-u-poljoprivredi-i-zivotnoj-sredini/
Local media	
	http://www.ruma.rs/portal2/jupgrade/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=9447:landsense&catid=204&lang=en&Itemid=66
	http://rtvcentarsrem.rs/ucenicima-poljoprivredne-skole-predstavljen-projekat-landsense/
Regional media	
	http://www.rtv.rs/sr_lat/vovodina/srem/monitoring-zivotne-sredine-putem-aplikacija_872465.html
	https://www.vesti.rs/Sport/Monitoring-zivotne-sredine-putem-aplikacija.html

9 Challenges

Within several workshops organised during Phase I, the participants reported their experiences of being involved in “citizen science” project and in regard to using CropSupport application. The participants’ feedback is presented below, which will serve as input for D4.4 Feedback and Evaluation of LandSense Demonstration Cases - Report I:

CHALLENGES RELATED TO THE USER ENGAGEMENT:

- Specific time table of the end users activities (examination time, holidays, winter seasons, etc.);
- Unpredictability of the weather conditions (e.g. condition for collecting data during February and March 2018 were particularly challenging because of high soil moisture level);
- Outdated mobile devices with poor hardware and software performance.

CHALLENGES RELATED TO THE USE OF CROPSUPPORT WEB APPLICATION

- The users reported no possibility to edit shape of a parcel once it is drawn. They only can delete it, but, in that case, the problem is that all associated data with that parcel will be deleted as well (e.g. activity timeline).
- Background Google map over which user delineates parcel is outdated and usually does not respond to the current crop rotation scheme. Hence, some users had not been able to precisely delineate their parcels.
- The Google map pinned icon that represented the photo of the parcel, does not indicate direction from which the photo was taken. This situation makes it difficult for a user to decide exact location of the parcel (e.g. is it on the left or right side of a road).

CHALLENGES RELATED TO THE USE OF CROPSUPPORT MOBILE APPLICATION

- The users suggested adding new functionality to the application – possibility to enter farm activities. Currently, it is only possible to enter the farm activity via web application.

All challenges presented above, particularly those related to improvement of CropSupport web and mobile application will be addressed in the upcoming period, i.e. until beginning of the Phase II pilot activities (February, 2019).

10 Next steps

The overall experience related to the involvement of the citizens in agricultural data collection provided valuable insights for planning the upcoming Phase II activities, where the real farmers will be engaged in crowdsourcing of agricultural in-situ data. As such, the next iteration of the pilot activities should start in February 2019. Here, a special effort will be directed towards improvements of data quality and user retention (in contrast to Phase I activities where quantity and user activation were in the focus).

The main upcoming activities in relation to preparation for the 2019 iteration include the following:

- creation of the precise plan and timeline of Phase II pilot activities, along with the INOSENS internal division of labour;
- the CropSupport mobile and web application improvements in line with the feedback received through the Phase I;
- integration of the Change Detection Service with the CropSupport application;
- communication with several farmer associations to reach and expand farmers base willing to participate in the Phase II pilot activities;
- adjusting the “Phase I information kit” to the Phase II requirements.

Annexes

Annex 1 – Photo gallery

Engagement: Workshop at the Agricultural High-School Bač

Engagement: Workshop at the Agricultural High-School Ruma

Engagement: Workshop at the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences

Figure 2. Engagement of target groups

Meeting with the students from the Agricultural High-School Bač

Meeting with the with the students from the Agricultural High-School Ruma

Meeting with the with the master students from the University of Novi Sad

Figure 3. "The end of the campaign" activities

Rewarding the most active students with working uniforms

Rewarding the high-school from Bač with a new laptop

T-shirts and USB sticks for the campaign participants

Rewarding the high-school from Ruma with a new laptop

Figure 4. Rewarding the participants of the campaign

Annex 2 – Social media announcements

Figure 5. Social media announcements

Annex 3 – Feedback workshop

Figure 6. Feedback workshop activities and the field trip (Sep 2018)